

**THE IMPACT OF INCOME INEQUALITY ON
ECONOMIC GROWTH:**

Evidence from U.S. State-Level Panel Data (1998–2018)

By

ISAAC LAMPTEY

Department of Economics
Drexel University

Date: April 2021

Isaac Lamptey | ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0256-8109>

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between income inequality and economic growth across U.S. states using panel data from 1998 to 2018. Economic growth is measured using real Gross State Product (GSP) per capita, while income inequality is captured using the Gini coefficient. Applying fixed-effects regression analysis, the findings reveal a statistically significant and positive association between income inequality and economic output, while unemployment exhibits a negative effect on growth. These results align with studies suggesting that, in high-income regions like the United States, income disparity may spur economic expansion. Limitations and avenues for further research are discussed, including the influence of additional socioeconomic and demographic factors not included in the model.

Keywords: Income Inequality, Economic Growth, Gini Coefficient, Unemployment, Gross State Product, Panel Data, United States

INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, the US as well as other developed countries have experienced an increase in income inequality as economic growth also continued to steadily rise. The purpose of this report is to explore the effects of income inequality on economic growth. This topic of discussion has been largely debated amongst many different researchers resulting in some inconclusive and/or conflicting results in their studies. In this report, I aim to find either a direct or inverse relationship between income inequality and economic growth.

The Organization of Economic and Corporation Development (OECD) reported in 2014 that the income disparity between the rich and the poor has worsened in the past 30 years. They further reported that income inequality between the upper-class families and poor families among the 37 OECD countries has increased by a ratio of 7:1. This pre-pandemic trend has been worsening since 2014. In 2015, the average income of wealthy families was 9.5 times more than lower income families, which has been determined to have a negative impact on sustainable growth (OECD, Income Inequality and Poverty). In 2019, The OECD released its most recent income inequality index report. This index, also known as the Gini coefficient, ranges from 0 to 1 representing complete equality and complete inequality, respectively. Out of the 37 countries, the United States was placed 33rd with a Gini Coefficient of 0.390 despite the US GDP of \$21.43 trillion reported by the Bureau of Economic Analysis of the Department of Commerce (Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020). Slovakia and Slovenia ranked 1st and 2nd respectively with a Gini Coefficient of 0.236 and 0.249 respectively while Costa Rica ranked 37th with a Coefficient of 0.478. (OECD Data, Income Inequality Index, 1976-2019)

To promote economic growth by encouraging opportunity and income equality, the General Secretary of the OECD said,

We have reached a tipping point. Inequality can no longer be treated as an afterthought.

We need to focus the debate on how the benefits of growth are distributed. Our report ‘In it Together’ and our work on inclusive growth have clearly shown that there doesn’t have to be a trade-off between growth and equality. On the contrary, the opening up of opportunity can spur stronger economic performance and improve living standards across the board! (OECD Secretary-General, <http://www.oecd.org/social/inequality.htm>)

In another recent study, evidence showed that there was a negative relationship between inequality and growth (Panizza, 2002). Contrary to the findings in (Partridge, 1997) which stated, “The Gini coefficient results suggest that states with more income inequality at the beginning of the period actually experience greater subsequent economic growth” (Partridge, 1997, p. 1030), Panizza’s research concluded that both the Gini Index and the income share of the third quintile are negatively correlated with economic growth (Panizza, 2002, p. 37). Also, in another study, Inequality, Growth, and Investment, conducted by National Bureau of Economic Research, they concluded that higher income inequality tends to promote economic growth in wealthy countries but retards growth in poorer countries (Barrow, 1999).

These sorts of variations in results are what I aim to resolve based on my own analysis of similar historical data. In previous studies, researchers have used the Gini Index as a measurement of income inequality within nations. I plan to use an index by the Bureau of Labor Statistics which produces the Gini Index of each State from 1917 to 2018 in order to determine if there is a significant direct or inverse relationship between income inequality and economic growth measured by the gross domestic product (GDP).

MODEL

This paper will analyze how income inequality affects economic growth. Economic growth is measured using Gross Domestic Product (GDP). GDP is defined as the economic output produced in a country at a particular period. The GDP of a state is called Gross State Product (GSP). GSP is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by state which is defined as the market value of the goods and services produced in a state at a particular period. To control for the effect of inflation on GSP, this paper will focus on the real GSP and not nominal. The population of a state also has a significant impact on its GSP. To account for changes in population in a given period of time, this paper will focus on the real GSP per capita which is defined as the economic output per person (GSP) divided by the state's population. The dependent variable (Y) to be used in this model will be the real Gross State Product per capita.

$$\text{Gross State Product per capita } (Y) = \frac{\text{Gross State Product}}{\text{Population}} \quad (1)$$

In this paper, income inequality will be measured by the Gini Coefficient of each of the 50 states that make up the United States of America. The Gini coefficient also known as Gini index is a measurement of income inequality within a group of people. The Gini coefficient is calculated using the Lorenz curve and the 45° line of equality. The Gini coefficient is equivalent to the size of the area between the Lorenz curve and the 45° line of equality divided by the total area under the 45° line of equality¹. The index of the Gini coefficient ranges from 0 to 1 representing complete equality and complete inequality, respectively. The more the Lorenz curve

¹ Refer to Figure 1

deviates from the line of equality, the higher the value of the Gini coefficient. In this model, the Gini Coefficient will be the independent variable denoted by X_1 .

Figure 1: Lorenz curve (calculation of the Gini coefficient)

Unemployment rate measures the number of eligible work force who do not have a job but are actively looking for one. Since the unemployment rate is correlated with the Gini coefficient² and has a significant impact on economic growth, according to Okun’s Law, it will be included in the model to prevent biased estimates of my coefficients. Okun’s Law is a popular rule of thumb that explains the relationship between unemployment rate and economic growth. According to Okun’s law, “For every 1 percentage point increase in unemployment rate, inflation-adjusted GDP drops by 2%. Due to this economic principle that explains the effect of

² Refer to Table 3

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unemployment rate on economic growth, this paper will also analyze the impact of unemployment rate, in each state, on the economic growth in the United States.

$$\text{Unemployment Rate} = \frac{\text{Unemployed People}}{\text{Labor Force}} \quad (2)$$

The econometric model to explain how income inequality affects economic growth in this paper will be represented by the regression function:

$$\text{GSP per Capita}_{it} = \beta_0 + \text{GiniCoefficient}_{it}\beta_1 + \text{Unemploymentrate}_{it}\beta_2 + v_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + X_{1it}\beta_1 + X_{2it}\beta_2 + v_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where Y is Gross State Product per capita (economic growth), β_0 is the intercept, X_1 is Gini Coefficient variable, β_1 is slope coefficient of X_1 which measures the partial effect of the of X_1 on Y controlling for the other regressors, X_2 is unemployment rate, β_2 is Slope coefficient of X_2 which measures the partial effect of X_2 on Y controlling other regressors, and v = error or disturbances.

Two other important variables within the data but will not be included in the model are wage distribution and jobs per population in each state.³ The wage distribution is also another measure of income inequality. It measures the ratio between the compensation of employees to the national income. The wage distribution is measured on an index ranging from 0 to 1. A wage

³ Addition of these variables affect the economic significance of the model.

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distribution index of 0 signifies that the entire wage earned in the United States is in the hands of a single family while 1 signifies that a much fair sharing of the national cake.

$$\text{Wage Share} = \frac{\text{Average Income}}{\text{National Income}} \quad (5)$$

Also, the total number of employment (jobs) per the population size is also an important variable in the data but will not be included in the model. Total employment includes all jobs including farm and non-farm employment. It also includes parttime and full-time jobs.

I hypothesize that the Gini coefficient and unemployment rate affect economic growth.

My null hypothesis (H_0) is that the Gini coefficient and unemployment rate have no effect on economic growth. My alternative hypothesis (H_a) is that at least one regression estimator affects economic growth.

$$H_0: \beta_1 = 0 \text{ and } \beta_2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$H_a: \beta_1 \neq 0 \text{ and / or and } \beta_2 \neq 0 \quad (7)$$

In another study, an empirical economic model that was used to show how Inequality and Redistribution affects Economic Growth was designed by Klaus Grundler and Philipp Scheuermeyer at the University of Wurzburg, Department of Economics. They used a model:

$$y_{it} - y_{it-1} = (\theta - 1)y_{it-1} + \lambda hit + \gamma \Psi_{it} + \delta R_{it} + \beta X_{it} + \eta_i + \zeta_t + v_{it} \quad (8)$$

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where $(y_{it}-y_{it-1})$ represents per capital GDP growth rates in a 5- year period, ξ_t represents time effects, v_{it} is the error term. The marginal effects of their variables of interest inequality and redistribution were captured in the coefficients γ and δ and the control variables are included in X_{it} . Their study further goes on to explain the causation of income inequality and redistribution by studying the effect of fiscal policy, saving rates and credit market imperfection influence on the Gini coefficient. This paper, however, will not address other factors influencing income inequality but will only focus on the effect of income inequality measured by the Gini coefficient, and unemployment rate on economic growth.

DATA

The panel data used in this paper were downloaded from different sources and combined to form a single database to be able to upload it into a statistical software for analyzation. The measures of income inequality data, the Gini coefficient, for each state is from 1917 to 2018 and was obtained from Bureau of Labor Statistics though not directly. A professor of Economics and International Business, Professor Mark W. Frank at the University of Sam Houston State University has a database with the links for easy access to the data from the Bureau of Labor Statistics. On the spreadsheet, I only included the years of importance to this paper (1998 to 2018)⁴. Among the data is the Thiel Index since this is also another measure of economic inequality but will not be included in this empirical research paper.

The data for the state population for two decades (1998 – 2018) was extracted from the United States Census Bureau. I also used a database from Harvard Scholars which has the direct links for easy access to the population data from the Census Bureau. Real State Product (RSP) from 1998 to 2018 and the GDP of the United States from 1998 to 2018 was obtained from the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, Department of Economic Research website. The data for the average income was also downloaded from the Federal Reserve Bank of St Louis website.

Summary of Results*Table 1: Summary of important variables*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
gsp p capita	1050	48831.416	9689.02	30412.389	79998.57
Gini	1050	.597 ⁵	.036	.522	.72
wage dist	1050	.287	.046	.196	.439

⁴ This is because data available for the other variable included in this paper were from 1998 to present.

⁵ The Gini coefficient of 0.597 is the mean Gini coefficient from 1998 to 2018 while the Gini Coefficient of 0.390 was the Gini coefficient of the United States in 2019 reported the OECD.

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unemplrate	1050	5.456	1.953	2.3	13.7
jobs p pop	1050	.598	.052	.478	.823

Note: gsp_p_capita is the real gross product per capita, wage_dist is the wage distribution, unemplrate is the unemployment rate and jobs_p_pop is the jobs available per population.

My data contains 1050 observations which includes data from all 50 states of the United States excluding Washington D.C and the unincorporated territories of the United States such as Puerto Rico, Guam, and the Virgin Islands. The overall mean real state product per capital is \$48,831.42 with a standard deviation of \$9,689.02. Also, from the summary above, the overall mean Gini coefficient is 0.597 while the mean wage distribution is 0.29. Overall mean unemployment rate is fairly low which is around 5.46% and each person in the 50 states have 0.6 job available to work. The detailed summary statistics that shows the mean values of only the key regression variables used in the model within the states and between each state from 1998 to 2018 is presented in the table 2 below. Figure 1 below also shows the scatter plot of the mean Gini coefficient of each state from 1998 to 2018 and their respective real gsp per capita.

Table 2: Detailed Summary statistics of key regressors.

Variable	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max	Observations
gsp_p_capita overall	48831.420	9689.020	30412.390	79998.570	N = 1050
between	8913.368	32874.450	71077.760		n = 50
within	3992.958	30906.390	70950.660		T = 21
Gini overall	0.597	0.036	0.522	0.720	N = 1050
between	0.028	0.554	0.670		n = 50
within	0.023	0.541	0.698		T = 21

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unempl~overall	5.456	1.953	2.3	13.700	N	=	1050
between	0.992	3.195	6.986		n	=	50
within	1.688	2.075	12.261		T	=	21

Table 2 above shows the detailed summary of the key regressors used in the model. It shows the mean value of each variable across the United States, the mean value of each regressor between the states and the mean value of each regressor within the states. From the table, between the individual states over the period of 1998 to 2018, the GSP per capita is \$8,913.37, the income inequality index is 0.028 while the unemployment rate is 0.992%. Within each state, the mean GSP per capita over the period of 1998 to 2018 is \$3,992.96, the mean Gini index is 0.023 and the mean unemployment rate over time is 1.68%.

Figure 2: Scatterplot of mean Gini Coefficient in each state from 1998 to 2018 (20 year averages)

RESULTS*Table 3: Correlation between the estimators*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)
(1) gsp_p_capita	1.000		
(2) Gini	0.219	1.000	
(3) unemplrate	-0.081	0.191	1.000

Table 3 above shows the correlation between the key regressors and the regressand. The Gini coefficient is positively correlated with gsp per capita while the unemployment rate is negatively correlated with gsp per capita. The Gini Index and unemployment rate are positively correlated. I will run a test to see if these correlations are statistically significant to understand how the increase in income inequality translates to higher economic output.

Since this is a panel data, I run a panel regression test for fixed effects (considering heteroskedasticity) using the panel data to be able to control both observed and unobserved time invariant or entity invariant to reduce omitted variables and produce unbiased estimates. The results are summarized in table 4 below.

Table 4: Fixed-effects (within) regression

gsp_p_capita	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Gini	68296.66	11961.533	5.71	0	44259.058	92334.261	***
unemplrate	-309.628	91.969	-3.37	.001	-494.448	-124.809	***
Constant	9723.878	7092.193	1.37	.177	-4528.417	23976.173	
Mean dependent var		48831.416	SD dependent var			9689.020	
R-squared		0.155	Number of obs			1050.000	
F-test		19.656	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		20220.174	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			20230.087	

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

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Since the p value < 0.05 , I will reject my null hypothesis that the regressors, Gini Index and unemployment rate, have no effect on the economic growth which means at least one of my chosen regressors has an effect on the real gross state product per capita (alternative hypothesis).

From table 4 above, with complete income equality (Gini = 0), and 0% unemployment rate (every eligible worker in the country has a job), the economic output increases by \$9,723.88 but this is not statistically significant since its p value is > 0.05 .

From table 2 above, the Gini coefficient, which represent the partial effect of Gini on gross state product (economic growth) controlling for unemployment rate is 68296.66. The economic interpretation is that, for every 1 percentage increase in the Gini Index, i.e., for 1 percent increase in income inequality, the economic output increases by \$68,296.66 (without changing unemployment rate).

The unemployment rate coefficient, which represent the partial effect of unemployment rate on gross state product (economic growth) holding the Gini Index constant is -309.628. The economic interpretation is that, for every unit increase in the unemployment rate, the economic output decreases by \$309.63 (without changing and Income inequality - Gini) assuming Okun's Law.

Some limitations of my analysis are that there are many factors that affect GSP and those factors were not included in the data. Some factors include other income inequality measures such as wage distribution, Palmer Ratio, Hoover Index, and the Galt Score of each state. Other variables excluded from the data that have as significant impact on economic growth which are also not included in this study include household size, educational attainment, and factors that cannot be directly measured such as infrastructure development, different labor laws across each state, migration within the United States, immigration of foreign nations into the United States,

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racial inequality and its impact on economic equity and socio-political conditions in each state. For example, a factor such as infrastructure development when high would lead to a higher GSP and will affect the number of jobs available per person within a state. Another example is educational attainment. States with more highly educated labor force will end up having a high GSP per capita and low unemployment rate since there will be more jobs created.

The study also does not address reverse causality between the unemployment rate and economic growth, the impact of the different economic boom and bust cycles on the unemployment rate and income inequality and how it affects the GSP. These are avenues for future research. I would have controlled for some of these variables if time had permitted. For example, factors such as infrastructure development could take on dummy variables with 1 representing states with highly developed infrastructure, such as New York and 0 representing “not highly developed” like Missouri. Also, I would have tested the effect of race and educational attainment on Gini Coefficient and how it affects the GSP per capita of the state.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of income inequality on economic growth using U.S. state-level panel data from 1998 to 2018. The analysis found a statistically significant and positive relationship between income inequality and real gross state product per capita, reinforcing the notion that income disparity may support economic performance in wealthier regions. This conclusion aligns with Barro's (1999) findings, which suggest that inequality tends to stimulate growth in high-income countries but hinders it in poorer ones. In contrast, earlier studies such as Panizza (2002) reported a negative association between inequality and growth—highlighting the ongoing debate within empirical economics.

As the United States is among the wealthiest nations globally, with a GDP of \$21.43 trillion in 2020 and a per capita GDP of approximately \$63,000 (IMF, 2020), this research contributes empirical support to Barro's hypothesis within a domestic context.

However, this study focuses exclusively on the Gini Index as the measure of income inequality and does not account for income distributions across specific quintiles or alternative indices such as the Theil index or wage share metrics. Moreover, it omits variables that significantly influence economic output, such as human capital, technological innovation, infrastructure development, labor laws, and intra-national migration. These exclusions limit the model's scope and suggest promising directions for future research.

Further studies could explore the granular effects of income distribution across population segments, test multiple inequality metrics, and incorporate cross-country OECD data to increase external validity. A multidimensional approach would deepen understanding of how

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economic growth interacts with inequality in both domestic and international contexts, informing more balanced and inclusive policy design.

REFERENCES

Barro, R. J. (1999). *Inequality, growth, and investment*. NBER Working Paper 7038.

<https://www.nber.org/papers/w7038>

Daily M. et al, *Interpreting Deviations from the Okun's law*, Federal Reserve Bank of San

Francisco Economic Letter. April 2014. [https://www.frbsf.org/economic-](https://www.frbsf.org/economic-research/publications/economic-letter/2014/april/okun-law-deviation-unemployment-recession/)

[research/publications/economic-letter/2014/april/okun-law-deviation-unemployment-recession/](https://www.frbsf.org/economic-research/publications/economic-letter/2014/april/okun-law-deviation-unemployment-recession/)

Department of Commerce, Bureau of Economic Analysis (2020).

<https://www.bea.gov/news/2020/gross-domestic-product-fourth-quarter-and-year-2019-advance-estimate>

Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, Economic Research: Gross Domestic Product by State.

<https://fred.stlouisfed.org/release?et=&ob=pv&od=desc&pageID=1&rid=140&t=annual%3Bgdp%3Bgsp%3Breal%3Bstate>

Grundler, and Scheuermeyer. *Income Inequality, Economic Growth and the Effect of*

Redistribution. Wuzberg Economic Papers No. 95, 2015.

Maio F., *Inequality Measures*, J Epidemiol Community Health. 2007 Oct; 61(10):849-

852. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2652960/>.

OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers <https://doi.org/10.1787/1815199X>

OECD (2021), Income inequality (indicator). <https://doi.org/10.1787/459aa7f1-en>

OECD (n.d.). *Inequality*. <http://www.oecd.org/social/inequality.htm>

Panizza, U. (2002). Income inequality and economic growth: Evidence from American data.

Journal of Economic Growth, 7(1), 25–41. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013414509803>

Partridge, M. *Is Inequality Harmful for Growth?* Comment. The American Economic Review,

87(5), 1019-1032, 1997. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2951339>

Schneider, D. “*The Labor Share: A Review of Theory and Evidence*”. SFB 649, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. (2011).

United States Department of Census Bureau. State Intercensal Datasets: 2010 – 2020.

<https://www.census.gov/data/datasets/time-series/demo/popest/intercensal-2000-2010-state.html>

United States Department of Census Bureau. State Population Data Totals and Components of Change: 2010 – 2019.

https://www.census.gov/data/tables/time-series/demo/popest/2010s-state-total.html#par_textimage

Watanabe A. “*US Census Bureau State Level Population Estimates 1990 – 2016*”: 2017.

https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/awatanabe/files/us_state_population_estimate_technical_notev1.pdf

“World Economic Outlook – GDP per capita”. International Monetary Fund. October 2020.